

Study of Equilibrium Constants of Beryllium(II) Ternary Complexes at different Ionic Strengths

VISHNU KOLHE

School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011

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Formation constants of 1 : 1 binary $\text{Be}^{\text{II}}\text{-L/L}'$ and 1 : 1 : 1 ternary $\text{Be}^{\text{II}}\text{-L-L}'$ complexes, where L = salicylic acid (SA), monosodium salt of 5-sulphosalicylic acid (SSA) and 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (DNSA) and $\text{L}' = 2\text{-hydroxyacetophenone (HAP), 2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone (DHAP) and 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone (CHAP)}$, have been determined potentiometrically in 20% (v/v) ethanolic aqueous medium at 25° and at three different ionic strengths of 0.15, 0.10 and 0.05 M (NaNO_3).

Survey of the literature reveals that some studies have been made on the binary and ternary complex formation ability of salicylic acid and salicylaldehyde and related ligands with Be^{II} metal ion¹ (but not with HAP, DHAP and CHAP). However, no attempt appears to have been made to determine the complexes using these ligands with Be^{II} ion.

The purpose of the present study was to obtain more precise information about the behaviour of the ligands in solution and stability constants of the complexes. In particular, it was tried to confirm the exact complexation equilibria of the complexes.

Results and Discussion

Binary complexing systems :

Be^{II}-SA/SSA/DNSA systems : In the $\text{Be}^{\text{II}}\text{-SA/SSA/DNSA}$ system, the metal-ligand titration curve is displaced with respect to ligand titration curve and giving inflection at $a = 2$, as a result of formation of the 1 : 1 binary metal-ligand species at $0 \leq a \leq 2$ and $\text{pH} \approx 4.0$. The interaction of Be^{II} with H_2L and HL^- species is possible and may be take place as

where, $\text{H}_2\text{L} = \text{SA/SSA/DNSA}$.

The ΔZ^2 values for reactions (A) and (B) are -2.00 and -4.00 respectively. Nature of the complexing equilibria can be confirmed by the extended Debye-Huckel equation,

$$\log K = \log K^0 + \frac{A \Delta Z^2 \mu}{1 + \mu} + e \mu$$

where, K^0 is the stability constant at zero ionic strength, A the Debye-Hückel constant, μ the ionic strength, ΔZ^2 is the difference in the sums of the squares of charges on product and reactant species and e the reaction constant.

The value of e was found to be 0.96. The ΔZ^2 values for the metal-ligand equilibria were calculated from the plot of

$\log K - e\mu$ vs $\mu/(1 + \mu)$. Taking the value of A as 0.509, the ΔZ^2 values for $\text{Be}^{\text{II}}\text{-SA/SSA/DNSA}$ chelates were found to be -2.00 , -2.02 and -2.01 respectively, indicating that SA/SSA/DNSA, i.e. H_2L combines with Be^{II} by equilibria (A). The binary complexes so formed undergo hydrolysis, as evidenced by the further divergence of curve on volume axis due to the liberation of extra one equivalent proton as a result of formation of monohydroxometal chelate species,

The occurrence of solid phase at $a = 3$ and $\text{pH} \approx 7.1$ further supports the formation of monohydroxometal chelate species. The values of hydrolysis constant of metal chelate are presented in Table 1.

Be^{II}-HAP/DHAP/CHAP systems : In all the metal-ligand titration curves of 1 : 1 $\text{Be}^{\text{II}}\text{-HAP/DHAP/CHAP}$, the metal-ligand curve diverges from the respective ligand titration curve at $0 \leq a \leq 1$ and $\text{pH} \approx 4.0$, indicating the liberation of extra proton as a result of 1 : 1 binary complex formation. The occurrence of yellowish green colour during the titration further indicates the formation of Be-HAP/DHAP/CHAP complex. The interaction of Be^{II} with both the species, i.e. HL' and L'^- is possible and 1 : 1 complexation may, therefore, take place following the equilibria,

where, $\text{HL} = \text{HAP/CHAP/DHAP}$.

The magnitude of ΔZ^2 for reactions (C) and (D) are -2.00 and -4.00 respectively. The calculated values from the ionic parameters are -2.01 , -2.00 and -1.99 for $\text{Be}^{\text{II}}\text{-HAP/CHAP/DHAP}$ respectively. It is, therefore, expected that 1 : 1 complexation occurs by equilibria (C).

Be-HAP/DHAP/CHAP system curves give inflection at $a = 2$ and $\text{pH} \approx 6.0$, indicating the formation of the monohydroxo metal chelate species. It is further supported

TABLE I

Proton dissociation constants :	$\mu = 0.15 M$		$\mu = 0.10 M$		$\mu = 0.05 M$		$\mu \rightarrow 0$	
	pK ₁	pK ₂						
SA	2.97	12.47	3.11	12.61	3.17	12.83	3.43	12.98
SSA	2.92	10.68	3.03	10.78	3.10	10.91	3.33	11.14
DNSA	1.51	7.37	1.66	7.52	1.98	7.75	2.12	7.96
HAP	10.62		10.78		10.92		11.14	
CHAP	9.79		9.95		10.15		10.35	
DHAP	10.08	11.96	10.21	12.09	10.35	12.18	10.63	12.39
Be ^{II} -H DHAP								
Be ^{II} -SA-HDHAP	9.14		9.21		9.29		9.46	
Be ^{II} -SSA-HDHAP	8.97		9.06		9.14		9.31	
Be ^{II} -DNSA-HDHAP	8.62		8.71		8.82		8.03	
Binary complexes :								
	log K _{MA} ^M		log K _{MA} ^M		log K _{MA} ^M		log K _{MA} ^M	
Be ^{II} -SA	12.34		12.41		12.50		12.68	
Be ^{II} -SSA	10.34		10.44		10.53		11.69	
Be ^{II} -DNSA	7.48		7.55		7.68		7.82	
	log K _{ML} ^M		log K _{ML} ^M		log K _{ML} ^M		log K _{ML} ^M	
Be ^{II} -HAP	9.18		9.26		9.35		9.54	
Be ^{II} -CHAP	9.06		9.13		9.21		9.42	
Be ^{II} -DHAP	9.15		9.24		9.31		9.51	
Monohydroxo metal ligand constant :								
log K _{M-SA(OH)}} ^M	-7.70		-7.78		-7.85		-8.03	
log K _{M-SSA(OH)}} ^M	-7.14		-7.22		-7.29		-7.46	
log K _{M-DNSA(OH)}} ^M	-6.35		-6.43		-6.51		-6.68	
log K _{M-HAP(OH)}} ^M	-6.33		-6.41		-6.50		-6.81	
log K _{M-CHAP(OH)}} ^M	-6.27		-6.36		-6.45		-6.61	
log K _{M-HDHAP(OH)}} ^M	-6.24		-6.30		-6.39		-6.57	

by the occurrence of turbidity at $a = 2$ and $\text{pH} \approx 6.5$ Equilibrium for this hydrolysis reaction is

Hydrolysis constants of binary complexes were obtained by using Bjerrum's functions³. The values are presented in Table 1.

Algebraic method⁴ has been used to obtain the values of proton dissociation constants of various ligands and formation constant of binary complex species. The formation constant K_{ML} for metal to ligand binary complex may be given as

$$\text{M} + \text{L} \rightleftharpoons \text{ML}; K_{ML} = \frac{[\text{ML}]}{[\text{M}][\text{L}]} \quad (1)$$

Thus the formation constant can be evaluated after calculating the values of [L], [M] and [ML]. Thus for the binary complex titration of 1 : 1 metal-to-ligand ratio, $C_L = [\text{H}_2\text{L}] + [\text{HL}] + [\text{L}] + [\text{ML}]$; $C_M = [\text{M}] + [\text{ML}] + [\text{ML}]'$; $aC_L = [\text{HL}] + 2[\text{L}] + 2[\text{ML}]$. Using the above equations and relations for the proton-dissociation constants of the ligand we get,

$$L = \frac{(2-a)C_L}{\frac{2[\text{H}^+]^2}{K_1^{\text{H}} K_2^{\text{H}}} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_2^{\text{H}}}} \quad (2)$$

where, K_1^{H} , K_2^{H} are the first and second dissociation constants of ligand. Therefore

$$\text{ML} = C_L - Y_1 L \quad (3)$$

$$\text{and } M = Y_1 L \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where, } Y_1 = \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{K_1^{\text{H}} K_2^{\text{H}}} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_2^{\text{H}}} + 1$$

Putting the value of [L], [M] and [ML] from equations (2-4) into (1) we obtain the value of K_{ML} .

Be^{II}-SA/SSA/DNSA-HAP/CHAP/DHAP system : In the ternary systems, the mixed ligand Be^{II}-SA/SSA/DNSA-HAP/CHAP/DHAP experimental titration curves overlap with those of the 1 : 1 binary Be^{II}-SA/SSA/DNSA experimental curves upto $a = 1.9$ and $\text{pH} \approx 4.5$ until the protons of primary ligands SA/SSA/DNSA under study are neutralised, indicating the formation of Be^{II}-SA/SSA/DNSA binary complexes and non-coordination of

 Fig 1. Potentiometric titration curves of Be^{II}-SA-HAP system

HAP/CHAP/DHAP with Be^{II}-SA/SSA/DNSA and Be^{II} ion upto this stage. The formation of ternary complexes supported by the divergence of the ternary Be^{II}-SA/SSA/DNSA-HAP/CHAP/DHAP experimental curves from the binary Be^{II}-SA/SSA/DNSA respectively, reveals the formation of ternary complexes of the Be^{II}-SA/SSA/DNSA-HAP/CHAP/DHAP through stepwise equilibria,

in which H₂L, i.e. SA/SSA/DNSA acts as primary ligand and HL', i.e. HAP/CHAP/DHAP as secondary ligand.

The values of $\Delta\log K$ for stepwise ternary complexes (Table 3) indicate that the HAP, CHAP and DHAP, i.e.

 Fig 2. Species distribution of Be^{II}-SA-HAP system; $\mu = 0.10$, $t = 25^\circ$.

HL, combine with Be^{II}-SA/SSA/DNSA in undissociate form according to the equilibria,

In case of SSA which is taken as H₂L⁻ species, the charge on the binary and ternary would be -1 and -2 respectively.

The formation of ternary complexes is further supported by the appearance of yellowish green colour during the titration of mixed ligand system.

At any pH in mixed ligand system,

$$C_M = [\text{M}] + [\text{ML}] + [\text{ML}'] + [\text{MLL}'] \quad (5)$$

$$C_L = [\text{H}_2\text{L}] + [\text{HL}] + [\text{L}] + [\text{ML}] + [\text{MLL}'] \quad (6)$$

$$C_{L'} = [\text{HL}'] + [\text{L}'] + [\text{ML}'] + [\text{MLL}'] \quad (7)$$

where, $C_L = C_{L'} = C_M$.

$$aC_M = [\text{HL}] + 2[\text{L}] + 2[\text{ML}] + [\text{L}'] + [\text{ML}'] + 3[\text{MLL}'] \quad (8)$$

TABLE 2

	$\mu = 0.1 M$ $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\mu = 0.10 M$ $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\mu = 0.05 M$ $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\mu \rightarrow 0$ $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\Delta\log K$	(%) R.S.
Be ^{II} -SA-HAP	6.96	7.03	7.16	7.38	-1.97	-21.07
Be ^{II} -SSA-HAP	7.10	7.19	7.27	4.47	-1.88	-20.11
Be ^{II} -DNSA-HAP	7.53	7.62	7.73	7.94	-1.41	-15.08
Be ^{II} -SA-CHAP	6.83	6.91	7.04	7.26	-2.26	-22.93
Be ^{II} -SSA-CHAP	6.97	7.05	7.13	7.32	-2.10	-22.90
Be ^{II} -DNSA-CHAP	7.41	7.51	7.60	7.81	-1.61	-17.09
Be ^{II} -SA-HDHAP	6.35	6.48	6.59	6.74	-1.83	-21.35
Be ^{II} -SSA-HDHAP	6.49	6.61	6.71	6.95	-1.62	-18.98
Be ^{II} -DNSA-HDHAP	7.17	7.25	7.38	7.59	-0.98	-11.44

where a is the moles of alkali per mole of metal ion in 1 : 1 : 1 MLL' system. From equations (5-8) and by introducing the dissociation constant of the ligands, we have

$$C_M (3-a) = a_1 [L] + b_1 [L'] \quad (9)$$

$$\text{where, } a_1 = \frac{2 [H^+]^2}{K_1^H K_2^H} + \frac{[H^+]}{K_2^H}$$

$$\text{and } b_1 = \frac{[H^+]}{K_1^H}$$

$$\text{Further, } C_M - C_L = [M] + [ML'] - [H_2L] - [HL] - [L] = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\text{and } C_M - C_L' = [M] + [ML] - [ML'] - [L'] = 0 \quad (11)$$

Introducing the dissociation constants of the ligands and the formation constants of the binary complexes, equations (10) and (11) can respectively be written as

$$[M] \{1 + K_{ML} [L']\} = a_2 [L] \quad (12)$$

$$\text{and } [M] \{1 + K_{ML} [L]\} = b_2 [L'] \quad (13)$$

$$\text{where } a_2 = \frac{[H^+]^2}{K_1^H K_2^H} + \frac{[H^+]}{K_2^H} + 1$$

$$\text{and } b_2 = [H^+]/K_1^H$$

Equating (12) and (13), then putting the value of $[L']$ from equation (9), we obtain

$$[L]^2 (a_2 K_{ML} b_2 d^2 K_{ML}') + [L]$$

$$(a_2 + db_2 + 2e, db_2 K_{ML} - (b_2 e_1 + b_2 e^2 K_{ML}') = 0 \quad (14)$$

$$\text{where, } e_1 = \frac{(3-a) C_M}{b_1} \text{ and } d = \frac{a_1}{b_1}$$

Solving the quadratic equation (14), the value of $[L]$ was obtained and only the positive roots of the equation (14) were considered. The values of $[L']$ and $[M]$ were then calculated from equation (9) and (12) respectively, and the concentration of $[ML]$ and $[ML']$ species were obtained as

$$[ML] = K_{ML} [M][L] \text{ and } [ML'] = K_{ML'} [M] [L']$$

finally the concentration of the mixed ligand species $[MLL']$, over the entire pH range, was calculated from equation (5) by substituting the values of C_M , $[M]$, $[ML]$ and $[ML']$.

The formation of ternary complexes can also be evidenced by representative species distribution curves for Be^{II}-SA-HAP is shown in Fig. 2. The metal-ligand stability constant of ternary complexes along with other related parameter, viz. $\Delta \log k$ and percent of relative stabilisation⁵ of the ternary complexes are given in Table 2. The values of $\Delta \log k$ and [(%) R.S.] are obtained from the following equations.

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{BeL'L}^{Be} - \log K_{BeL}^{Be}$$

$$(\%) \text{ R.S.} = \frac{\Delta \log K}{\log K_{BeL}^{Be}} \times 100$$

The numerical values of (%) R.S. are used for a quantitative estimation of the relative stabilisation of the ternary systems at a given temperature and ionic strength. Larger negative value of (%) R.S. indicates lesser stabilisation and larger positive value indicates greater stabilisation of the ternary complex with respect to binary complex. In the present investigation, negative values of $\Delta \log K$ and (%) R.S. indicate that the ternary complexes are less stable than the binary complexes, i.e. secondary ligand binds better to $[Be^{II}H_2O]^{2+}$ ion than to the binary $[Be^{II}-L]^0$ complexes. Such a higher stability of the binary complexes compared to that of the ternary complexes is due to the greater attraction force between the Be^{II} and secondary ligand than the $[Be^{II}-L]^0$ binary complex and secondary ligand due to the greater ionic potential of Be²⁺ than $[Be^{II}-L]^0$ complex. While in case of SSA, electrostatic repulsion between $[Be^{II}-SSA]^-$ and secondary ligand coupled with the availability of lesser number of coordinating sites for the second ligand on $[Be^{II}-L]^0$ compared to free Be²⁺ aqueous ion.

For a series of similar ligands, the higher the basicity of the ligand the greater is the stability of the metal $[Be^{II}-L]^0$ and $[Be^{II}-L']^+$ binary complex and ternary complexes with respect to secondary ligand, i.e. SA > SSA > DNSA (binary complexes) and HAP > DHAP > CHAP (binary and ternary complexes). Stability order of the ternary complexes with respect to primary ligand is DNSA > SSA > SA, which is the reverse order of the basicity of the primary ligand. It can be explained on the basis of the fact that the electron-withdrawing nature of nitro or sulphonic group present in DNSA and SSA respectively, is making Be²⁺ effectively more electropositive in $[Be^{II}-L]^0$ complex, this enables to form more stable complexes with respect to salicylic acid.

TABLE 3 -VALUE OF ΔZ^2 OBTAINED FROM THE SLOPE S $A = 0.509$

Compd.	Exptl values obtained from slope	Compd.	Exptl. values obtained from slope
Be-SA	-2.00	Be-SA-CHAP	-2.00
Be-SSA	-2.02	Be-SSA-HAP	-2.03
Be-DNSA	-2.01	Be-SSA-DHAP	-2.01
Be-HAP	-2.01	Be-SSA-CHAP	-1.99
Be-DHAP	-2.00	Be-DNSA-HAP	-2.00
Be-CHAP	-1.99	Be-DNSA-DHAP	-2.01
Be-SA-HAP	-2.03	Be-DNSA-CHAP	-2.02
Be-SA-DHAP	-2.01		

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Solutions of SA, SSA and DNSA were prepared in CO₂-free double-distilled water while those of HAP, CHAP and DHAP in absolute ethanol. Beryllium nitrate solution (0.01 M) was

standardised by usual method⁶. An Elico LI 120 pH meter fitted with glass and calomel electrodes was used.

Procedure : Six solutions (total volume 50 ml in each case) of the following compositions were prepared : (I) HNO_3 ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$); (II) (I) + ligand H_2L ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$); (III) (II) + metal ion ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$); (IV) (I) + ligand HL' ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$); (V) (IV) + metal ion ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$); (VI) (I) + ligand H_2L ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + ligand HL' ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + metal ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$). Appropriate amount of NaNO_3 solution ($1.0 M$) was added to maintain the desired ionic strengths (i.e. 0.05, 0.10, 0.15 M). The mixtures were thermostated at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$ and titrated pH-metrically against 1.0 M NaOH solution. For the sake of brevity, titration curves obtained at $\mu = 0.1 M$ (temp. = $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$) have only been given in Fig. 1. All the experiment of binary and ternary system were performed in 20% (v/v) ethanolic aqueous and appropriate correction in pH-meter readings were made⁷ to get true pH value. In ethanolic aqueous medium, proton dissociation constants, stability constants of 1 : 1 bi-

nary and 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes increase with decrease in dielectric constant of the solution.

References

1. V. K. ZOLOTUKHIN, *Ukr. Khim. Zh.*, 1983, 49, 349 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1983, 98, 50222); M. M. MAEDA and I. K. YUTAKA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1987, 1853; M. LAJUNEN, H. J. LAURI and A. KORTAMA, *Acta Chem. Scand., Part A*, 1979 33, 681; H. J. LAURI and M. LAJUNEN *Acta Univ. Quluensis*, 1978, 74, 21 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1979, 91, 12973); P. DAS and R. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 547.
2. F. J. C. ROSSOTTI and H. ROSSOTTI, "The Determination of Stability Constants", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1961.
3. J. BJERRUM, G. SCHWARZENBACH and L. G. SILLEN, "Stability Constants", Chemical Society, London, 1957, Part I, and 1958, Part II.
4. R. NAYAN and A. K. DEY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 892; R. NAYAN, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, 43, 383.
5. S. N. LIMAYE and M. C. SAXENA, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1986, 56, 292.
6. H. A. FLASCHKA, "EDTA Titration", 2nd ed., Pergamon, New York, 1964.
7. L. G. VAN-UITERT and C. G. HASS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 451; U. B. RAO and H. B. MATHUR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 3, 1234.